

Juxtaposing Nigeria's federal-presidential system and the United States (us): Implications of Nigeria's political system on its political stability

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Abstract

The study, juxtaposing Nigeria's federal-presidential system and the United States: Implications of Nigeria's political system on its political stability, delves into the discourse of the issues surrounding Nigeria's political system, highlighting similarities and differences between the political systems of both countries. The study states that issues like demand for restructuring, resource control, over overcentralization are associated with deficiencies in Nigeria's federal structure. Same with the presidential system, which is stifled by a powerful, dominating executive with little or no checks from the other branches of government, including also an over-bloated and one of the most expensive run executives in the world. The study acknowledges the fact that though both countries operate the same political system with basic tenets, processes, and operations. However, the United States (US) has maintained and strengthened its political systems and stability than Nigeria over time. The study adopts the systems theory as its framework of analysis. The method of study is qualitative using historical research. Findings reveal that discontent and disenchantment of citizens over the failure of the political system to provide the much-needed democratic dividends have led many Nigerian citizens to alienate self from politics, while there exists a leadership hijack of the political process amongst other problems. The study recommended that a change of political system is not the answer to Nigeria's political crisis, rather a consensus agreement on constitutional review and commitment to the existing political system, and the aim of good governance by the ruling class.

Key words: Presidential system, Political Stability, Social development, Sustainable development

Introduction

Countries all over the world adopt different systems of government to suit their diverse socio-political society. The choice of political system are mostly dependent upon internal factors such as; history and culture, geography and demography, ideological

beliefs, level of economic development and as well as other external factors. Thus, the preferred political system must offer some form of functionalities to

address unique challenges of the said political society.

While some countries have adopted and maintained a particular political system from the inception of their State creation thus learning from the inherent weaknesses in the political system and also devising means of strengthening such a system. Others have rather chosen to jettison a type of political system for another, after realizing the

inability of the political system to address peculiar fundamental challenges. There are however others which have merged at least two types of political systems to align with their socio-political realities.

There are various examples of political systems such as the United States (US) a foremost practitioner of presidential and federal political system. It has maintained its presidential-federal nature since the State formed. Nigeria on the other hand had jettison an earlier adopted unitary structure for a federal framework in 1957 and a presidential political system, believing that this political structures have the capacity to make room for the diversity. The United Kingdom has also maintained a parliamentary system for so long that it has become a foremost practioner of this type of political system. Russia, Mexico and France have opted for mixed political system; a combination between parliamentary and presidential to suit their clime.

The focus on political systems and institutional framework of governance has garnered much attention due to diverse forms of political crisis which is being experienced by the various countries all over the world especially developing nations arising from demand for good governance and its dividend by dissatisfied citizens who have had opportunity to make comparison between the development in their countries and others which have sometimes led to serious civil unrest. This comparison has easily been enabled through advancement in information and communications technologies which has helped in identifying deficiencies in political system and other related causes such as leadership factors.

Nigeria and U.S.A not only operate the presidential system of government, both countries have also adopted a federal system as a structure of governance. The presidential system is popularly known for having a chief executive in the person of the president who is the head of state, government

and the commander in chief. Major hallmarks of this system includes separation of power and functions between executive, legislature and judiciary. It also entails checks and balance system meant to create oversight functions by each of three organs of government over each other, while the federal structure makes constitutional provision of shared powers and functions between the central and the constituents units of governments.

Historically both countries were ex-colonies of British government, though both gained their independence under different circumstances. According to Haus and Hausman (2013) the US fought a revolutionary war to gain her independence from Britain in 1776 and later began its presidential system in 1789, Nigeria on the other hand gained its independence in 1960 through a peaceful negotiation and transition to independence (Adigwe:1977). According to Oyeneye, Onyenwenu and Olusunde (2006), it was not until 1979 that Nigeria adopted the presidential system of government after earlier attempting a parliamentary system which was bequeathed to her by erstwhile colonial power.

Similarities of exist in their basic institutions like; executive, legislature, judiciary and other relevant democratic institutions like political parties, pressure groups, civil societies organization, professional association amongst others. Areas of differences are however noticeable in the extent or degree of political processes and resultant outcomes in the form of policies and decisions of government. Significant differences also lies in the numbers of ministries or departments, agencies of government and in powers and limitations of person(s) with authority entrusted with governance. Other important variable which significantly impact on the outcome of the political systems in both countries includes; political culture, pattern of interest, pattern of power and pattern of policy.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria has been bedeviled with diverse socio-economic and political problems since attaining independence in 1960. Problems such as ethnic - religious conflicts, election crisis, corruption, minority agitations for recognition, demand for equitable distribution of State resources and political appointments, impact of long years of military rule, general failure of governance which has resulted in increasing poverty , unemployment, deteriorating social service delivery, increasing insurgency, terrorism and a whole lot of problems that have become an endemic challenge.

In particular recognition of problems with ethnic diversity and other anticipated challenges, in 1957 three years before independence, a federal state structure was adopted to encourage self rule, promote growth and development in the regions to discourage a possible stagnated parochial politics of contentions at the center. It was also meant to foister unity amongst diverse nations that make up the Nigeria State. Again in 1979, the presidential system was adopted to address political conflicts arising from the the divisive nature of the parliamentary system of government as practiced in Nigeria which had led to a series of conflicts, culminating in the advent of military coup in Nigeria.

The presidential system and federal structure which were adopted as measures to address the foundation challenges of politics in the Nigeria State have been subverted from its original framework and intentions thus resulting not only in the failure of governance but the system posing a significant threat to the political stability of the State Ibeanu (2017). For example, the Nigeria's federalism has been described as a "federation without federalism" according to Babalola (2017) who ascribes his position majorly to the failure of the lower federating unit to autonomously operate in its sphere of influence with its assigned constitutional powers without interference from the center undermining it. The concentration of power at the center,

centralization of State's revenue and monopoly of the State coercive apparatus is inimical to the doctrine of federalism as promoted by Wheare (1953).

The continued demand for restructuring, autonomy, resource control attest to a disproportionate political arrangement. In theory, while the Nigeria State is known as a federal State, in practice, it operates unitary system. The federal government exert significant control and influence over regional governments and subsidiaries, thus reducing these levels of government to a state of economic servitude and redundancy without much initiative to develop self despite monthly fiscal allocations.

Another challenge of the political system is the nature of presidential system which is being practiced in Nigeria. The operation of this system undermines democracy and constitute a serious challenge to governance. Whereas the hallmark of this system rest on the separation of powers amongst the three basic organs of government with each having oversight over the other. In Nigeria however, the executive arm of government which is headed by the president assumes an almost dictatorial power thus making president a very powerful political actor not easily subject to the rule of law and more often without proper checks from the other institutions of government. The implications of this, is the existence of abuse of law, arbitrary use of government powers and the State machinery by the executive to further private ambition especially against oppositions thus enabling human rights abuses and violations.

A major challenge of Nigeria's presidential system also is the high cost of running this political system. The extravagant life style and remuneration of the political elites which involves duplications of offices, agencies and ministries used mostly as payback for political favors. Awotokun (2020) asserts that this has led to an over bloated political

system that not only bleeds the nations resources dry but has led to an hyper inflation.

Furthermore, the practice of these twin systems have impacted on the political stability of the Nigerian State by undermining democracy, encourage leadership failure, instigated political conflict in the polity and brought untold economic hardship on the Nigerian people.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of this study is to compare the institutional framework of governance between United State of America (USA) and Nigeria's, explaining the implications of Nigeria political system on its political stability. Specific objectives are to;

- i. Examine similarities and differences between the Nigeria and United States presidential-federal systems
- ii. Examine the setbacks of Nigeria's presidential system and federal structure of government and implications on its political stability.
- iii. Proffer possible solutions to the challenges associated with Nigeria political system.

Conceptual Clarification.

Federal State. The term federal or federalism are used interchangeably to describe a form of government where there exist defined divisions of powers and functions between central and regional or component units of governments. Such powers are usually divided into two or three categories; the exclusive list, residual list and concurrent list.

Appodorai (1975) defined a federal State as one in which there is central authority that represent the whole, and acts on behalf of the whole in external affairs, and in such internal affairs as are held to be of common interest; and in which there are also

provincial or State authorities with powers of legislation and administration within the sphere allotted to them by constitution.

The distinctive features of a federation is thus, the formal division of governmental powers by a constitution between constituents units (federal, region and local government), the supremacy of the constitution which embodies the supreme laws of the land. Therefore the federal constitution operates a rigid constitution.

A constitution which is usually written for the sake of practical necessity outlines the framework of relationship between the centre and components units of governments. Several conditions encourage the adoption of a federal State, they include the desire for unity among diverse groups which seek to maintain autonomy, common historical experience, geographical proximity and the need to secure protection from a strong union.

Presidential System of Government: This is a system of government whereby the chief executive of a State in the person of the president who is at the same time, the head of the executive organ of government. He or she also exercises control over the affairs of the State within a stated constitutional provision. The United States has been a foremost practitioner of this system which was adopted by it since 1789.

The presidential system is usually described as the direct opposite of the parliamentary system which is commonly identified by a fused system between the executive organ and the legislative organ of government. However the presidential system is characterized by a fixed tenure of office, a doctrine of separation of powers amongst the three major organs of government; executive, legislature and the judiciary with checks and balances.

Political System: Political System is that system of interaction in any society through which binding and authoritative allocation of value are made and

implemented. A political system performs functions that are both integrative and adaptive through its claim of the legitimate use of force, more or less. Every political system involves political structure, political roles performed by actors or agents, patterns of interaction between actors which could be individuals or groups, and also a political process.

Political Stability: political stability is a concept used to assess or measure stated political phenomenon in a given political system. It enables comparative analysis and ranking of entities such as rule of law and human capital development. Furthermore, it refers to a condition in which a country's government is secure, functioning effectively and able to provide predictable and peaceful environment for its citizens. Thus, the key characteristics of political stability includes, consistency in governance, rule of law, peace and security, economic prosperity and social cohesion.

It is important to state that political stability is in levels and thus a country like Nigeria could be observing periodic elections and transition of government from one government to another yet can be considered to be unstable because of its failures in some of the core political stability indices such as deficit in the areas of; authority, legitimacy, monopoly of the use of force and failure to provide basic social services which are indicated the state fragility theory.

Literature Review

The institutional framework of governance of USA and Nigeria refers to the various institutions of governance and the set of internal rules, roles, relationship, rights and obligations, responsibilities and functions of government. It also entails government relationship with the electorate, the public consumer of services and also non-state actors. According to Tonwe (2016) governance goes beyond the political system, it includes the totality of all sectors that relates with political actors.

The Nigeria's political system is tailored after the USA political system that is famously known for its presidential and federal system of government. As a constitutional federal republic the powers of the US government are shared between national and state governments. The president of the US does not only represent a symbol of power of the State of US but he is regarded as a very powerful actor in the international world stage. Despite this enormous powers of the US president, his actions are usually in accordance to the American's constitution and Congress decisions.

Haus and Hausmann (2013) asserts that the founders and framers of the America political system created a State in which multiple, overlapping level of authority prevent anyone person, group or party to get what he wants unless through negotiations, thereby forcing all actors to seek compromise to problem. The United States president has to do more persuading more than most democratic leaders because America political institution deny him the tools that facilitate executive leadership unlike the parliamentary system. Heywood (2007) also avers to this position when he said that though the politically privileged and economically powerful exerted greater power than ordinary citizens in United States however no ruling or permanent elite was able to dominate the political process in the history of United State

In comparison to the US, the Nigeria's federal-presidential system of government like many other political systems in the Sub Saharan countries in Africa has an eroded separation of powers and checks characterized by weak Institutions. The executive institution represented by the president has hegemony over all other institutions of governance. Eregha (2004) and Bena' Baku (2015) explained that the president is not only seen as very powerful but also having wide discretionary powers which avails him the use of state machinery to sometimes further

his inordinate ambition resulting in flagrant abuse of power and impunity.

The US federal structure which is designed to incorporate the diverse people and their interests into one united government with a sense of belonging was done through consensus by the parties in a constitutional agreement and judicial decisions for by the former 13 colonies that came together to form the United States in 1776 serving as the basis for unification of US. The Nigeria State lacked such consensual agreement in its amalgamation process of 1914. This unification which later birthed the present federal structure in Nigeria has raised questions of unity and nation building.

Ikelegbe (2016) contends that the failures and eventual collapse of the first republic necessitated the need for a powerful executive and even more powerful centre despite the Nigeria State not having a sense of nationality. This shift to centre culminated in the adoption of a presidential system further impeded on the objectives of federalism. Thus the large stake of the power at the center has become a primary guarantor of material advancement, making competition for State a do or die battle.

Basic Institutions of Government and Functions: Similarities and Differences in the United States and Nigeria Political Systems.

i, The Executive; this institution amongst the three arms of government has the primary function to prepare national budget, implement laws and policies, recommend legislature and conduct foreign policy. The president has the power to veto legislation, appoint judges and grant reprieve and pardon.

Similarities: The U.S and Nigeria have the same fixed term of four years term with basic constitutional powers.

Differences: The framework of electing the chief executives of both countries are different. Whereas the Electoral College system is used to elect the US president from any of the two dominant political parties of the Democrat or Republican, Nigeria uses a simple majority with a condition of two third majority from multi party system. Again the number of ministries in Nigeria or departments in the US are wide apart. While US have 15 department with 15 secretaries as head of department, Nigeria have at least 28 ministries with about 44 ministers.

ii. Legislature: Three basic functions of this institution are; lawmaking, representation and oversight powers. Other discretionary power includes confirmation of presidential appointment, approval and rejection of international treaties negotiated by executive, a charge of impeachment against the president and Supreme Court judges and all bill intended to raise revenue which must be passed from congress.

Similarities: both countries have a bicameral legislature made up of the Senate and Representative House of Assemblies with a four year tenure.

Differences: in Nigeria, four senators are elected from each state of the federation, while in US two senators are elected from each state with the senators in the Congress grouped into three groups with each group expected to run for office in every two years. According to Haus and Hausman (2013) this procedure is to ensure that there are always experienced senators in the House at any time but more importantly it signals the important mid-term election that determines the US president fate in office.

Another important difference between the US Congress and the Nigeria national assembly is that whereas the Congress is able put a check on the US president as was witness in their stand against Donald Trump second term election, when he wanted

to overturn the 2020 US presidential election in his favor leading to his false claim of election rigging which eventually led the January 6, 2021 insurrection (Associated Press: 2025). The Nigeria legislature, however are unable to challenge obvious manipulation of election by a sitting president

iii, Judiciary: This institution has the unique powers to arbitrate on constitutional matters between executive and the legislature and any other legal matter in the land.

Similarities: courts in both countries are subdivided into levels of powers and areas of specialities with the Supreme Court being the highest court of the land.

Differences: one significant factor that has impacted on the justice system on both countries is the presence or absence of judicial autonomy. In US, there exist judicial autonomy, beyond the fact that budget of the judiciary do not have the appendage of the executive arm of government, the judges in the Supreme Court in the US are appointed for life thereby making them impervious to political pressure.

In Nigeria on the other hand, not only are supreme court judges appointed by the chief executive, the fiscal budget of the judiciary is under the purview of the executives making this important arm of government subservient to the executives. Also supreme court judges are meant to retire at 70 years unlike US.

iv. Political Parties: They serve as one of the basic tenets of democracy, an organized group with similar ideological framework mobilized to capture political power.

Similarities; Both countries have political parties.

Differences: In US individuals and groups form political parties based on very strong ideological

linings and share their common beliefs and passion. They also contribute financially to fund and support this beliefs and passion. In Nigeria however political parties lack ideological foundation. Most of the popular political parties like People Democratic Party (PDP) and Action People's Congress (APC) and others are not known for any specific ideological positions rather political aspirant emphasizes manifestos during political campaign represent. This document represent electoral promises which are easily reneged.

Another issue with the Nigeria party politics is that elected politicians easily crossover to other political party especially to the political party in power without consequences of losing their mandate. In Nigeria political parties are mostly seen as investments structure by the political elite to acquire political power for self, maintain it and translate it to the desired choice of candidate, preferably a family member.

v. Electoral Institution: In Nigeria the agency entrusted with the conduct of elections, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) has severally been criticized for truly not being independent. Omeme, Ibeanu and Onyishi (2017) asserts that there have alleged agency connivance with the ruling party thus resulting in more disputed election that are usually decided in court and mostly won through legal technicalities since the period of uninterrupted civil rule from 1999. In USA the reverse is the case cases of electoral irregularities are hardly recorded due to the integrity of the electoral body and confidence placed on the electoral agency the by the United States citizens. For example, the allegation of election irregularities by Donald Trump in the 2020 election led to the recounting of votes in some states yet result proved the same.

On rights, while there are no State exempted from rights abuses and violations, United States is known globally for protection of civil liberties. While Nigeria has a low record of upholding human rights according Mo Ibrahim Report (2020). Also the long years of military rule has instilled a culture of coercive enforcement of law and order.

- vi. Civil Societies Organization (CSO) / Human Rights Organizations: Activities of CSO and Human Rights Organizations are very active in US. They are able to mount significant pressure on government to overturn unpopular government policies. Whereas in Nigeria CSOs largely relies on foreign actor such as State and non- state actors to pressure government to act on popular will. On human rights abuses, Nigeria and States within the sub Saharan region ranks low amongst commity of nation on life expectancy and human rights protection Mo Ibrahim Report (2020).

Challenges of Nigeria's Political System.

Beer and Ulam (1968) cited in Bena'Baku gave a fourfold analysis of a political system which includes; pattern of culture, pattern of interest, pattern of power and pattern of policy. This fourfold variable determine outcome in a political system. The questions arising from these four areas would be; what is the pattern of Nigeria's political culture? Whose and what interest are served by the Nigeria political system and to who does this interest serve? Who are the power actors of this system? and what are the outcome of the policies of this system.

The answers to these questions largely lies in the foundational framework and processes of the Nigeria's political system which have either enables or hinders integration, corruption, growth and development of the Nigeria State. The Nigeria political system favored more negatives on these various account.

Arising from unresolved issues of fundamental imbalance in the political system and deficit political processes which fanned embers of suspicions, anachronistic regionalization, ethno- religious conflicts, fears of minority domination and other issues bedeviling the nation's integration and nation building. At independence in 1960, the country was on a very shaky socio - political, economic and cultural foundation. For example, there was no truly national party that commanded nationwide support and loyalty.

Between 1960 to 1965 the Nigeria State experienced political upheavals which significantly threatened Nigeria's political stability. Some of these issues includes; the crisis and loss of confidence following the 1964 elections, the census crisis that lingered between 1962 to 1964 due to politicisation, the breakdown of law and order in the Western region in 1965 region and the eventual intervention of military coup. Subsequent challenges which have threatened the country's stability till date are the issues, the challenge of conducting free and fair election, weak Institutions government, corruption, failure of ruling elites to provide good leadership, the increasing insecurity which has led to kidnapping, terrorism and banditry.

These issues have continued to plague the Nigerian State due to political system and processes that is not properly aligned to its original form. Critical attributes of government that determines its capacity to perform its onerous role includes; legitimacy, support of citizens, competence of political leadership and sound people oriented policies and programmes, amongst others which are lacking. The failure of governance through it leaders to operate within the rubrics of the critical areas of both systems is attributed to the deficit in federal structural and weak presidential system that is practiced in Nigeria compared to the US.

Separation of powers and checks and balances which serve as basic tenets of Presidential system of government has also been compromised on the grounds of ethnicity, religious and corruption in governance in Nigeria. The inability of the three main organ to fully carry out its statutory responsibilities due to the primordial nature of politics the political system and governance has become the undoing of this system.

Some of the challenges attributed to deficit in the Nigeria's political system are;

- i. Lack of credible election and election violence
- ii. Lack of national integration and continued agitations by group (s) for restructuring and autonomy
- iii. Unlimited power of executive branch of government and high cost of governance
- iv. Ineffectiveness of constitutional and political mechanism
- v. Governance issues in the security sector and mismanagement to security threats
- vi. Violation of rights and freedoms of citizens
- vii. Leadership crisis
- viii. Deepening retrogression of development, economic decline and acute poverty.

Implications of Nigeria's Weak Federal - Presidential System on its Political Stability.

While there are many implications of Nigeria's political system, the discussion will highlight three area of grave concerns to the nations democracy and nation building.

1. The Challenge Political Apathy by Citizens. According to Awotokun (2020), political system are expected to fulfill some basic aspiration of citizens political needs that enables political participation thereby

promoting a vibrant political system where there exist a continues flow of input, output and feedback for the survival of the political system. Failure to do this creates disenchantments with the said political system. Attitude such as voters apathy and self alienation from political responsibilities are expressed with every election in Nigeria and also commitment the State and government is lacking (Ohiorenuan and Omosefe: 2020).

In Nigeria, every election further exposes the failure of the political system and unwillingness of the political class to get it right. The consequence of this is that democracy is bought by the highest bidder and legitimacy is lost.

2. Crisis of Leadership. One of the challenges of governance in Nigeria has been identified as leadership failure. Weaknesses in the Nigeria's political system created a niche for mediocrity in the political space through a culture of lawlessness, impunity which was created by abuse of power by the executive organ of government. The lack of legitimacy of leadership has become serious factor of governance. Citizens are unwilling to accept leader's from a skewed political process which is seen to be compromised. This has hindered integration and nation building thus promoting ethnic divisions.

Weak Regional Governments: According to K.C. Wheare cited Mahajan (2013), a federal system must have a sort of balance which will ensure all units maintaining their some level of independence within the constitutional sphere allotted them. By this, regional and other levels of government are able achieve self- reliance through comparative economic advantage.

In Nigeria many regional governments which are also referred to as state governments which were

created lack the ability to function with comparative advantage or become self-sufficient within the federal structure of the Nigerian state. Rather, these states were created based on parochial sentiment of religion and ethnicity, and other factors, thus have become inept and completely dependent on the center.

Conclusion.

Nigeria and the U.S share a similar institutional framework in their adoption of a federal-presidential system. The similarities in the political system for both countries are mostly found in the establishment of the basic tenets. However for Nigeria it lacked the required processes and the degree of adherence to the required standard to the rules of this political system.

The operation of federal system in Nigeria lacks the full benefits of what a federal system ought to be in line with the doctrine of autonomy and shared power and function. The Nigeria federal system is more unitary nature thus permitting over centralization. Also the Nigeria's presidential system of governance is marked by the dominance of the executive branch over the other branch of government with an almost dictatorial chief executive. Again the presidential in Nigeria is more expensive to run compared to US which it borrowed its system from.

The adoption of federal - political system by Nigeria can be said to be more in theory than practice, adherence to the rules are lacking. Parochial tendencies of ethnicity and religion weakens institutions and output of government.

Despite the problems associated with the federal - presidential system of government in Nigeria it is important to state that leadership factor play a more significant role in the workability of both systems, as there exist no perfect political system in world. Abandoning this political system that is the presidential system as have been suggested by some

concerned citizens, may not be the answer. Moreover over the system is working in the US.

The problem is not situated in the political system, but in the players of this system. On this, leadership plays a significant factor. The ruling elites over time, have introduced parochial sentiment as the basis of governance, thus weakening the political system. Again, the issues of corruption have not only compromised the standard of governance but also set out a standard that derailed the functional workability of the political system by the actors.

Theoretical Framework

The study adopted the Systems thoery as a tool for analysis. This thoery is particularly relevant in explaining a juxtaposed Nigeria's federal-presidential system and the United States: Implications of the Nigeria political system on its political stability. This is because theory helps in understanding the outcome of a subverted systems and the relationship. For example, one can explain that the different outcome of the same political systems in Nigeria and United States is product of the environment of operations.

The central preposition of the systems approach is that all social, including political phenomenon are interrelated and they affect each other. It is assumed that it is not possible to understand one part of the society in isolation from the other part which affects its operation.

Systems thoery in political science made popular by David Easton. Some other proponentd of this approach include scholar such as Gabriel Almond, Karl Deutsch, Herbert Spiro amongst others. While this this thoery has been criticized for being too abstract for its inability to delineate between political system and other systems in the society however one can argue its relevance in explaining the reality of political

Methodology of the Study

The study adopted an historical research design using secondary and progressive data to explain the juxtaposed Nigeria's federal - presidential system and the United States: implications of Nigeria's Political system on its political stability. Secondary data were used include books, journal and other online information. Data were analyzed by content analysis technique.

Recommendations

1, it is recommended that wholestic constitutional review by a civilian democratic population is required to rejig the basic tenets and modalities of operations of the Nigeria's federal - presidential systems of government. This should also be implemented through the popular will of the people and political elites.

2, The study recommend that the three basic institutions of government should maintain their independence to enable proper check and balance on each other as it is done in the US. This should be accompanied with judicial autonomy.

3, The study further recommend that federating units should be allowed to be self-sustaining thus policy framework be formulated to reflect this position, by this, more attention should be paid solely to its constitutional responsibility. The federal government should discourage its overbearing influence.

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